

Corporate Leadership: A Study of the Psychodynamic Skills in Growing in the Corporate World

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ABSTRACT

Corporate world is changing as their leaders undergo personal transformation and move toward self-actualisation, and then bring their perspectives and values to the office. Corporate are also changing from within, as the people that make up those corporate are quietly asking and in some cases demanding, social and accountability and meaningful work. Leadership is both a deeply personal and a highly interpersonal undertaking. Applying psychodynamic concepts to the ebb and flow of life in corporate contributes to the understanding of the vicissitudes of corporate leadership. The psychodynamic paradigm, when applied to corporate leadership, draws only on psychoanalytic theories of human behaviour, but also the work of many later scholars and thinkers in other fields who adapted and broadened the foundation concepts of psychoanalysis to encompass the hidden and overt dynamics that influence the behaviour of groups and even corporate. As such a psychodynamic approach provides valuable frameworks and concepts for studying the shaping many facets of corporate leadership. In this paper, it is argued that psychodynamics skills are playing a vital role in shaping an effective corporate leader and its role is growing in the growing corporate world, with special reference to post globalisation.

Keywords: *Psychodynamic Skills, Corporate Leadership, Personality Traits, Character Strengths, Five-Factor Model*

Background

Corporate leadership faces unprecedented challenges in constant findings new ways to lead successfully. Corporate principles, practices and behaviour need updating and change to create sustainable success (Petrick, 2014). Corporate leadership also needs to change the behaviour of stakeholders to meet the global changes for corporate to sustain success (Sethuraman & Suresh, 2014). However, this change can be achieved through the gaining of knowledge. As Drucker (1985), the father of modern management, stated, today knowledge has power. It controls access to opportunity and advancement. Following Drucker's wisdom, Rock (2009) postulates that improving corporate effectiveness, followers and leaders performance starts with improving leaders' knowledge of how behaviour is created.

It is imperative the research studies the impact of effective corporate leaders on corporate, the workers and their environments, maximising the efficiency, productivity and performance. Effective leaders lead corporate to prosperity (Popa, 2012). Leaders are the backbone of corporate. Researchers have analysed the backbone for what defines and develop an effective corporate leader (Yuki, 2012). Corporate leader's personal characteristics are a crucial component of be successful corporate and contribution to the corporate environment (Derue, Nahrgang, Wellman & Humphrey, 2011). The early years of corporate leadership research debated if leadership traits were inherited or influenced by nature

(Northouse, 2010). Because scholars could not find one single genetic trait or a combination of genes, researchers switch to analyse the corporate' situation and environment influencing the leader's behaviour and characteristics (Papworth, Milne & Boak, 2009).

Statement of the Problem

Many corporate firms attempt to improve their success by developing corporate leadership through training courses and cultures. Large amounts of money are spent for executives to attend leadership courses, classes, workshops and other training sessions where the goal is to define and develop skills that will lead the corporate through effective leadership behaviours. Hyper focus on leadership styles, behaviours and skills can create an environment where the attention is solely on the corporate leader and not the strategic outcome of the leadership behaviours or the impact of the followers and employees.

The most researched standard reoccurring problems, issues or questions of leadership research appears to be what is the cause of leadership efficiency and how to maximise it. The importance of corporate leadership expanding efficiency, performance and productivity of the leaders, followers and corporate has received much attention over the centuries. It peaks in the last decade with the latest research on authenticity, neuroscience, authentic leadership and neuro-leadership. Researchers of studies on animals, human twins, communities and molecular genetics techniques estimate the genetic and psychodynamic involvement in behaviour, physical and mental health emotions, energy, spirituality, cognition, attitude and other human characteristics exist, leading to well-being (Powledge, 2011). Simultaneously, vast research exists on effective psychodynamic leadership skills that have led to enhancement of performance in corporate (Yuki, 2012). However, there is a deficiency of scholarship regarding the investigation of the link between psychodynamic skills, effectiveness and leadership. Therefore, this quantitative research was an exploration of corporate leaders with the knowledge of psychodynamic skills seeing themselves as aspiring to be more effective corporate leaders.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to explore how the knowledge of psychodynamic skills affects the

corporate leadership. It added to the academic literature on effective corporate leadership behaviours. An attempt was made to explore how psychodynamic skills affect the corporate leadership. Also, the study investigated whether corporate leaders with the knowledge of psychodynamic skills applications have the perception of maximising their efficiency, performance and productivity of themselves, followers and the corporate.

The study of corporate leadership and personality is not only a search for understanding the thoughts and actions of corporate leaders but also a search for how to improve the performance and motivation of both individuals and groups. It is generally well accepted that corporate leadership is a complex experience whereby both the person and the situation influence actions. Given the importance of corporate leadership to the success of groups, corporate and even entire civilisations, there are few more pressing questions. However, only in the past century has corporate leadership effectiveness become an area of significant study. Although much research concerning personality and corporate leadership has been conducted, few studies have examined the relationship between a corporate leaders' personality and their leader effectiveness longitudinally.

Significance of the Study

Intuitively, the behavioural tendencies should have an impact on the ability to lead effectively. Previous studies have used trait based instruments to identify the behavioural tendencies that are relatively stable over time that correlate with successful corporate leadership. Over the past two decades, the Five Factor Model of personality has become the golden standard measure of personality (Hogan et al., 1994; Judge et al., 2002). However, previous findings have been inconsistent in determining the strength of personality traits as predictors of corporate leadership effectiveness over time (Judge et al., 2002).

Part of the limitations of this research has been the inconsistency stemming from different measures of personality traits. Another important limitation has been the quality of quantifiable measures of leader effectiveness. A third limitation has been the lack of longitudinal studies correlating personality traits with leader effectiveness. This article provides a unique contribution to the literature by assisting in clarifying the inconsistent findings in the relationships between personality and leadership effectiveness.

Research Questions

The study examined the following research questions:

1. What is the combination of personality factors and virtues that best predict corporate leadership effectiveness?
2. Are there any latent class variables of personality traits and character strengths that provide a trajectory of corporate leadership effectiveness?

Hypothesis

H₀: The necessity of psychodynamic skills is not growing in the corporate world in the era of post globalisation.

H₁: The necessity of psychodynamic skills is growing in the corporate world in the era of post globalisation.

Literature Review

From recent headlines to historical data about the business, the number of business failures and unprofitable bottom lines suggests that some people who become executives are neither successful nor competent. It basically then follows that there are varying levels of leadership competence (Bass, 1990).

The major impact of trait research on leadership and goal achievement is its conclusion that traits endow people with the only potential for leadership (Bass, 1990; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991), not for leadership. Somehow, traits must be applied in situations to achieve goals. To implement core traits, such as adaptability, control of moods, cooperation, dominance, competence, emotional control, initiative, intelligence, persistence, ambition, honesty, insight, goal setting etc., additional factors are necessary. Two core traits appear correlated with corporate leadership competence and goal attainment – intelligence and honesty (Bass, 1990).

Leaders are generally characterised as being intelligent (but not necessarily brilliant) and as being conceptually skilled. An intelligent mind, strong analytical ability, good judgement and the capacity to think strategically are necessary for effective corporate leadership. In short, leadership requires above average intelligence not necessarily genius (Kotter, 1982; Bass, 1990; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991).

Honesty appears essential to corporate leadership. Honesty refers to keeping one's word, to being truthful and no deceitful (Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991). Honesty forms the foundation of trusting relationships between leaders and their followers. Effective leaders are credible, with excellent reputations and high levels of integrity (Bass, 1990). Honest leaders may be able to overcome their lack of expertise in some areas (Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991). Bass, Avilio and Goodheim (1987) conclude that leaders who did not fulfil their agreements were viewed as less effective by their subordinates.

Some theories indicate that certain core traits significantly contribute to a corporate leader's success. Leaders differ from non - leaders in their drive, their desire to lead, their honesty/integrity, their self - confidence, their cognitive ability and their knowledge of the business (Bennis & Nanus, 1985; Bass, 1990; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991).

Leader's self - confidence plays an important role in decision making and in gaining others' trust. If leaders are unsure in their decision making or express a high degree of doubt, then followers are less likely to trust them and commit to the leaders' vision (Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991). Consequently, others' perception of a leader's self - confidence is important for getting followers to follow.

Emotional stability is essential in resolving interpersonal conflicts or representing any corporate. Top executives who act impulsively will not foster the same level of trust and teamwork as executives who retain emotional control. Leaders who lack emotional stability and composure are more likely to derail (Bass, 1990; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991).

Charisma, creativity, originality and flexibility are traits will less clear-cut evidence of a relationship to leadership (Howard & Bray, 1988; Bass, 1990; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991). Effective corporate leaders may or may not, have charisma; however, this trait may be more important for political leaders than others.

One area of growing interests in both the corporate world and the psychology of leadership is identifying the defining positive personality strengths. There are two schools of thought related to strength – viewing them as talents or virtues. One school led by Buckingham and Clifton (2001), believes that personal strengths are extensions of people's talents,

something that manifests itself as a naturally recurring pattern of thought, feelings or behaviours. Here strength stems from a talent and is a near - perfect performance of an activity and every time a person performs it.

Donald Clifton, in general, is believed to be the grandfather of positive psychology – a pioneer in the area of strengths research (Lopez, Hodges & Harter, 2005). Clifton believes that talents can be operationalised and investigated. Two principles are embedded in strengths. First, for an activity to be the strength, there must be the consistent performance of that activity. Second, the strength does not need to be present in all aspects of an individual's life for that person to excel. By maximizing strengths, individuals will become the best at their profession (Buckingham & Clifton, 2001).

The Personality Debate

The debate over the existence or absence of personality structures is less divisive now than it was 20 years ago (Graziano, 2003). Virtually all of the studies that correlate personality and leadership assume that personality is a stable trait. Many theories emphasize its enduring nature and ignore the potential impact of time (Biesanz, West & Kwok, 2003). However, in order to assess the validity of studies that relate personality and leadership across time, a review of research on personality stability and change in young adults is necessary.

Some theories, such as Roberts, Caspi and Moffitt have argued that personality development ends by age 5 or even before this (2001). In the middle of the spectrum, Costa and McCrae have argued that personality is fully formed and stable by age 30 (1986; 2000). At the other end of the spectrum, Lewis contends that personality development continues across the lifespan (1998).

Five-Factor Model

Throughout the past century, scholars have sought to classify personalities by looking at both subordinate traits and super ordinate factors. Some researchers have developed measures which assume that there are only three constructs (Eysenck, 1991) or four constructs (Myers, McCaulley & Most, 1985). Others have attempted to capture personality measures under the umbrella of 16 or more constructs (Cattell, Eber & Tatsuika, 1970; Megargee, 1972). What all these

researchers have in common is that they suggest that a common taxonomy or factor approach exists to classify personality types.

Fiske (1949) identified a five-factor model (FFM) for classifying individual behaviour. Fiske labelled the initial five factors as extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability and culture. In the FFM, the hierarchical factors consist of numerous distinctive subordinate traits and behavioural tendencies (McCrae et al, 1989). McCrae and Costa (1985) also designated five factors of personality. These five-factors are oftentimes referred to as the “Big Five” and include agreeableness, conscientiousness, extraversion, neuroticism and openness. Several studies correlating personality and leadership effectiveness have suggested the use of the FFM (Hogan et al., 1994; Judge et al., 2002).

The first factor within the model is agreeableness. Agreeableness refers to the quality of interpersonal relationships (DeNeve & Cooper, 1998). Hogan et al., (1994), defined agreeableness as a measure of an individual's sympathy, cooperation and warmth. According to Piedmont (1998), agreeableness includes the facets of trust, straightforwardness, altruism, compliance, modesty and tender-mindedness.

The second factor is conscientiousness. Conscientiousness or constraint refers to task behaviour and impulse control (DeNeve et al., 1998). Conscientious individuals work hard, persevere and are organised (Hogan et al, 1994). Furthermore, conscientiousness includes the facets of competence, order, dutifulness, achievement, self - discipline and deliberation (Piedmont, 1998).

Extraversion, the third factor, focuses on both the quality and intensity of relationships (DeNeve et al., 1998). Extraversion is sometimes referred to as surgency. Extraversion includes the facets of warmth, gregariousness, assertiveness, activity, excitement seeking and positive emotions (Piedmont, 1998).

The fourth factor, Neuroticism refers to lack of adjustment and is inversely related to emotional stability (DeNeve et al., 1998). Neurotic individuals are impulsive, irresponsible and not dependable (Hogan et al., 1994). Neuroticism includes the facets of anxiety, hostility, depression, self - consciousness, impulsiveness and vulnerability (Piedmont, 1998).

The fifth and final factor is openness or openness to exercise. Openness concerns an individual's ability to be imaginative, broad-minded and curious (Hogan et al., 1994). Openness includes the facets of fantasy, aesthetics, feelings, actions, ideas and values (Piedmont, 1998). Overall, the FFM provides an opportunity to explore the relationship between personality and leadership effectiveness.

Character Strengths and Virtues

In contrast with the FFM, Peterson and Seligman have attempted to measure character strengths and virtues (2004). Virtues are the core traits valued necessary for an individual to possess good character. Character strengths are the psychological processes underlying the broad categories of virtues. Although derived utilizing two separate approaches to understanding behavioural tendencies, the positive psychology literature on character strengths appears to have a similar composition to Five Factor Model.

According to Peterson and Seligman's (2004) exploratory factor analysis of scale scores using varimax rotation, they suggest the strengths correspond with five superordinate factors (strengths of restraint, intellectual strengths, interpersonal strengths, emotional strengths and theological strengths). In addition, they suggest that the first three factors correspond to the Big Five Factors of conscientiousness, openness and agreeableness. Also, emotional strengths might be inversely related to the Big Five Factor of neuroticism. Only theological strengths (i.e. gratitude and spirituality) did not appear to have a corresponding Big Five Factor (Peterson et al., 2004).

Personality and Leadership

As noted earlier, there is a relationship between personality and leadership. The major objective of this section is to analyse and clarify inconsistencies in the personality and leadership literature and to identify which characteristics of personality are likely to influence leadership effectiveness.

Early studies of traits and corporate leadership were conducted by Stogdill (1948) and Mann (1959). Although Stogdill found inconsistent results in the studies he examined, a significant relationship between intelligence and leadership emerged. Later, Mann (1959) examined the relationship between personality and perceptions of small group leadership.

Especially, Mann sought to examine attained the status of individuals in leaderless groups. While the studies included in this review did not focus especially on leadership effectiveness, Mann found small but significant relationships between leadership and personality traits. However, possibly due to later misinterpretations, these two reviews led to the common belief that personality was not effective in the prediction of later leadership.

Personality Traits Correlated with Leadership Effectiveness

Twenty-six years after his initial review, Stogdill's (1974) second review supported the notion that leadership is related to personality. Especially, Stogdill found positive relationships between leadership and agreeableness (i.e., friendliness), conscientiousness (i.e., achievement), extraversion (i.e., dominance, assertiveness and sociability) and openness (i.e., self - confidence). Clarifying this earlier work, Stogdill's (1974) review concludes that personality and leadership are significantly interconnected.

Several other studies have consistently linked personality with leadership attributes. Avolio, Dionne, Atwater, Lau and Camobreco (1996) predicted leadership styles using personality constructs. Atwater & Yammarino (1993) examined the relationship between personal attributes and perceptions of leadership. Other studies have examined personality traits and obtained rank within a corporate (Vickers, Hervig & Booth, 1996). Still, other researchers sought to incorporate what is known about personality research into selection criteria for jobs that require effective leaders (Helton & Street, Jr., 1992; Street, Jr., Helton & Nontasak, 1993). Overall, there has been strong evidence that some personality traits are related to leadership (Batlis & Green, 1980).

Methodology

There are two principal research paradigms can be used in business research, namely – the positivistic and a phenomenological / interpretivism paradigm. According to Bryman and Bell (2007), positivism is an epistemological position that advocates the application of the methods of the natural sciences to the study of social reality and beyond. The role of positivism as stated by Anderson (2004) resides in searching for facts in terms of clarifying the

relationship between variables before identifying a data collection pattern through statistical approaches as followed in quantitative research procedures. According to Collis and Hussey (2003), the positivistic approach concentrates on facts and the causes of social events, paying modest respect to the subjective state of the individual.

The quantitative research is built on a numerical measurement of specific characteristics related to a phenomenon. Quantitative approaches employ deductive logic, moving from the general to the specific. The tools used to carry out quantitative research tend to be surveys and questionnaires (Coombes, 2001). It is a very structured approach and is most often focused on objectivity, generalisability and reliability (Collis & Hussey, 2003). The key advantage of the quantitative approach, therefore, is that it is based on fact and reliable data that enables researchers to generalize their findings to the population from which the sample has been drawn. A non-experimental research design is an appropriate approach to determine if a specific treatment (psychodynamics of a corporate leader) influences an outcome (corporate leadership skills and effectiveness of the corporate) using a sample that is not randomly assigned to a treatment or comparator group (Creswell, 2014).

A questionnaire according to Collis and Hussey (2003) can be used to gather data when the issues which arise are likely to be confidential and sensitive and give respondents more time to consider their answers. The questionnaire survey, as defined by McDaniel and Gates (2002) is comprised of a set of questions designed to generate the evidence necessary to accomplish the objectives of the research study. It is a method of getting answers to the research questions based on designing specific questions to be answered by the research participants (Robson, 2004; Bryman, 2004). Questionnaires as a survey method may be viewed as a comparatively simple and uncomplicated means of examining participants' attitudes, values, beliefs and motives. When the survey includes sensitive issues, a questionnaire affords a high level of confidentiality and anonymity (Robson, 2004).

The questionnaire consisted of five close-ended questions with an open-ended section at the end of the questionnaire for participants to add any further

comments about their perception of the psychodynamic skills. The response scales took the form of the Likert Scale. The Likert scale is one of the most widely used response scales in research and is used to evaluate behaviour, attitude or another phenomenon on a continuum. Rating scales simplify and more easily quantify peoples' behaviours or attitudes (Leedy & Ormrod, 2005). A neutral response option has not been given which might prove a bit disastrous if the majority of the respondents decide to choose this, thus posing a danger of not being able to conduct an optimal evaluation.

The sample size is a significant characteristic of any empirical study in which the goal is to make assumptions about a population based on a sample. Indeed, the sample size used in the study was determined based on the data collection figures and the need to obtain sufficient statistical power (Saunders et al., 2009). Saunders et al. added that the larger the sample size, lower the likely error in generalizing to the population.

The survey was distributed to a purposeful sample of 300 participants includes corporate leaders from a different spectrum, represents different areas of specialization and comprises different sectors. Statisticians contend that as a sample size increases, variability (i.e., effort variance) decreases and power increases. As power increases to detect a false null hypothesis, there is an increased risk of falsely rejecting a true null hypothesis.

Analysis

The survey asked a series of questions in order to establish whether there is a relationship between psychodynamic skills of a corporate leader and the effectiveness of the corporate. And the focus of the research and the survey is to find out whether the prominence of psychodynamic skills is increasing in the growing corporate world. This section provides a summary of the information that was collected through a questionnaire. The following tables and figures provide a snapshot of psychodynamic skills of a corporate leader.

Table 1: Self-confidence

	Indicator	Disagree			Agree		
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	In your opinion, a leader believes in himself/herself and his / her abilities.	42 (14)	102 (34)	144 (48)	45 (15)	111 (37)	156 (52)

Survey respondents were asked whether a corporate leader believes in himself/herself and his / her abilities. Around 52% of respondents expressed that corporate leader should possess self-confidence and believes oneself.

Figure 1: Self-confidence

Table 2: Persistency

	Indicator	Disagree			Agree		
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
2	In your opinion, a leader stays fixed on the goals, despite interference.	63 (21)	78 (26)	141 (47)	93 (31)	66 (22)	159 (53)

Survey respondents were asked whether a corporate leader should have persistence and goal oriented. As good as 53% of respondents positively responded that a corporate leader should possess the skill of persistence and goal focussed attitude.

Figure 2: Persistency

Table 3: Tolerance, Tactful and Sympathetic

Indicator	Disagree			Agree		
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
3 In your opinion, a leader shows tolerance, is tactful and sympathetic.	48 (16)	90 (30)	138 (46)	63 (21)	99 (33)	162 (54)

Survey respondents were asked whether a corporate leader should possess the virtues of tolerance, tactful and sympathetic. Around 54% of respondents agreed that a corporate leader should possess the virtues of tolerance, tactful and sympathetic.

Figure 3: Tolerance, Tactful and Sympathetic**Table 4: Commitment and Action Oriented**

Indicator	Disagree			Agree		
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
4 In your opinion, a leader takes a firm stand and acts with certainty.	54 (18)	81 (27)	135 (45)	60 (20)	105 (35)	165 (55)

Survey respondents were asked whether a corporate leader should be committed and action-oriented. A good number of respondents which consists around 55% agreed to the opinion that a corporate leader should be firm and action-oriented.

Figure 4: Commitment and Action Oriented

Table 5: Organised

Indicator	Disagree			Agree		
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
5 In your opinion, a leader is thorough, organised and controlled.	30 (10)	96 (32)	126 (42)	63 (21)	111 (37)	174 (58)

Survey respondents were asked whether a corporate leader should be thorough, organised and controlled. As high as 58% of respondents expressed their positive response that a corporate leader should be thorough, organised and controlled.

Figure 5: Organised

Table 6: Comprehensive

	Indicator	Disagree			Agree		
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Total	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	In your opinion, a leader believes in himself/herself and his / her ability	42 (14)	102 (34)	144 (48)	45 (15)	111 (37)	156 (52)
2	In your opinion, a leader stays fixed on the goals, despite interference.	63 (21)	78 (26)	141 (47)	93 (31)	66 (22)	159 (53)
3	In your opinion, a leader shows tolerance, is tactful and sympathetic.	48 (16)	90 (30)	138 (46)	63 (21)	99 (33)	162 (54)
4	In your opinion, a leader takes a firm stand and acts with certainty.	54 (18)	81 (27)	135 (45)	60 (20)	105 (35)	165 (55)
5	In your opinion, a leader is thorough, organised and controlled.	30 (10)	96 (32)	126 (42)	63 (21)	111 (37)	174 (58)
Total		237 (79)	447 (149)	684 (228)	324 (108)	492 (164)	816 (272)

Note: The figures given in parentheses indicate percentages of participants and non-participants. The value of Chi-square (χ^2) is 0.854 between participants with disagree and agree. The table values at 5 percent with 4 degrees of freedom are 9.48.

6: Comprehensive

In order to measure the impact of Psychodynamic Skills, the corporate leaders with disagreed compared with the agreed. The table shows that overall 228 percent of the total participants were disagreeing and 272 percent were agreed to consist five indicators. Chi-square (χ^2) test shows the significant difference and positively accepted the hypothesis regarding the leaders believe, interference, sympathetic, acts with certainty and organized leadership. As the obtained value is higher than the tabulated value, the null

hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Summary

A vast number of corporate around the world, complain that there is a dissonance between what their leaders say and what they do. This will remain a truism if those corporate leaders are not able to reflect on their own behaviour and that of their followers. It

is ironic that, while people see value in learning new skills, they rarely see value in looking at the ingrained character patterns they bring to the use of those skills. Yet it is those very patterns that dictate their behaviour and their decisions. As long as such patterns are unconscious, corporate leaders struggle to align espoused theory with practice.

Leadership studies are often faulted for causality problems, thus making it difficult to prove how leadership impacts outcomes for a social group or corporate (Bass & Bass, 2008). Psychodynamic leadership research theories sometimes meet resistance given the emphasis on interpretive methods. However, Prins (2006) suggested that the subjective experiences of the researcher within the psychodynamic paradigm can be in fact used productively as additional data. Loch (2010) outlined an interesting framework connecting the psychodynamic approach with the management science paradigm. Loch (2010) argued that bringing together the systems view, where roles are important for an understanding of managerial phenomena, with a psychodynamic perspective which seeks an integrated understanding of manager's motivation, could help overcome the limitations of both approaches in figuring out what actually takes place in the world of modern corporate.

As it became apparent that the hidden dynamics of individual leaders and groups could influence corporate outcomes, the issue of how to develop corporate leaders also became more topical. Corporate leaders themselves realised this and sought to include human issues in strategic planning. In answer, by the early 2000s most leadership development interventions, whether in business schools or incorporate, began to include experiential opportunities for participants to revisit their past experiences and reshape their future goals, on an individual, group and/or systematic level (Kets de Vries & Korotov, 2007, 2011).

Chang and Diddams (2008) also warned that leaders must be aware of the human tendency to self-deception and should be capable of dealing with "self-insight flaws." Chang and Diddams thus introduced humility as a key concept in leadership, which they argue implies an openness to concede imperfections that is not contingent with humiliation or loss of self-esteem, but rather, indicates an orientation towards others and away from self-preoccupation. In other

words, they warned against delimiting leadership with exclusively positive characteristics.

Despite these challenges and concerns, an increasing number of practitioners and scholars have come to realise that the use of psychodynamic concepts can provide greater insight into the vexing problems concerning individuals, groups and corporate systems. A burgeoning interest in related topics such as corporate leadership, corporate culture, career dynamics, leadership coaching, group behaviour and corporate change and transformation has focused attention on the psychodynamic point of view (Kets de Vries, 2011).

The psychodynamics provide new insights not only on how people become leaders but also how they interact with followers and how their individual psychodynamic history can influence the equilibrium of corporate systems. At the same time, equal attention must still be paid in the programs to skill building and technical expertise. Otherwise, a psychodynamic sensitivity to the vicissitudes of corporate life may eventually fall out of favour as a valid leadership competency. Similarly, although psychodynamic issues arise from human experience and are therefore universal, not all cultures or worldviews are equal in the way these issues are addressed. In the final analysis, therefore, it is essential to be aware of the psychodynamic undercurrents inherent in corporate leadership, but above all, do no harm.

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